

ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS OF WOMEN OF SAMARKAND REGION

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Annotation: From the first days of independence, among the numerous social problems of our country, significant attention was paid to the improvement of the condition of women, their wide involvement in the process of active participation in the country's social and political life, and solid legal foundations were established for the implementation of policies in this field. . One of the great achievements of Uzbekistan's humanitarian policy in the next five years, the state policy regarding women has changed radically. The published "Iron Book", "Women's Book" and "Youth Book" are modern effective methods of state policy aimed at increasing the social status of women, realizing their potential, and ensuring the process of integration and socialization of this category of people into the life of society. is being recognized.

Keywords: "Iron Notebook", "Women's Notebook", "Youth Notebook", "Financial Assistance", "Families in Need", "Women and Girls", "Social Support of Youth", " The most exemplary family", "Educated family", "Bookish family".

It is known that in different historical periods, this or that society has had support layers. In particular, in almost all societies, the differences between women and men are taken into account, and the established gender roles have certain consequences for the lives of men and women. In this case, certain "criteria" influenced the mutual activity and interaction of individuals and created the place and position (status) of women and men in the social structure. Now, as a result of certain "orders", today in many countries of the world, women do not consider themselves equal to men, this situation has arisen because they have been treated as second-class citizens for centuries. From this point of view, researching the issue of gender equality and its modern theoretical and methodological foundations as a regional problem is considered to be of urgent importance in the field of history.

Now, at the world level, the determination of true equal rights of women and men is considered as the basis of social progress and sustainable development of society. Therefore, the principles of equal rights and non-discrimination are consistently developing and strengthening in all international legal documents in the field of human rights. In this regard, it is no coincidence that since 1996, the UN has introduced another index of humanitarian criteria. This index is related to the provision of concrete equality between women and men, the expansion of women's rights and opportunities, and the elimination of gender inequality.

From the first days of independence, among the numerous social problems of our country, significant attention was paid to the improvement of the condition of women, their active participation in the social and political life of the country, and solid legal foundations were established for the implementation of policies in this field. Analysis of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan indicates its compliance with international standards in the field of

human rights. In particular, in Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in 1992: the principle of equal rights of men and women is strengthened.¹

At the same time, the daily life of women, who make up half of the population of Uzbekistan, their specific problems are considered as a matter of great social importance. Here, if we take a brief look at the demographics of women, the permanent population of the republic has increased by 13.9 million people over the last 30 years. According to the State Statistics Committee, in 1991, 50.6% of the permanent residents of the republic were women. This indicator was equal to 49.7% on January 1, 2022. In 2020, the largest percentage of regions in the total population of the republic was 11.4 percent in Samarkand region, followed by 11.1 percent in Fergana region, 9.7 percent in Kashkadarya region, and 9.7 percent in Andijan region. 2 percent. In this year, 50.3% of the population of Uzbekistan consisted of men, and 47.7% were women.²

It should be noted that one of the great achievements of Uzbekistan's humanitarian policy in the next five years, the state policy regarding women, has fundamentally changed. Regarding the nature of the policy in this regard, President Sh. Mirziyoyev stated that "in a society where the rights and interests of women are ensured, there will certainly be peace, justice, freedom and prosperity."

In order to ensure the effective implementation of laws related to the field, a draft of the strategy for ensuring gender equality in the years 2020-2030 of the Republic of Uzbekistan was prepared. This document is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men", the five priorities of the Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the priorities established in the Action Strategy until 2030. was developed in accordance with national goals in the field of sustainable development and other legal documents.³

In this regard, it should be noted that for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament has reached a level consistent with the recommendations set by the United Nations. The country's parliament has risen to 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of female deputies. 5 years ago it was on 128th place. In general, today's progress in ensuring gender equality in our country is primarily the result of the work carried out on the basis of the new system of social support for women.

Among them, on the initiative of the President, Women's Problem Councils were established in 9,255 neighborhoods, which listen to the pain of women in need of social protection and help solve their problems. The published "Iron Book", "Women's Book" and "Youth Book" are modern effective methods of state policy aimed at increasing the social status of women, realizing their potential, and ensuring the process of integration and socialization of this category of people into the life of society. is being recognized.⁴

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated January 8, 2021 "On additional measures for social support of women and girls" was adopted.⁵

¹ Gender expertise of the Family and Labor Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent, 2008. -B.6.

² <https://www.stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/demography>

³ Kenjaeva H. The role of civil institutions in increasing women's social activity // «Scientific Progress» Scientific Journal. Volume: 1, Issue: 6. - B. 959.

⁴ A woman is the cradle of life, a great and respected teacher // People's word, January 12, 2022.

⁵ <https://t.me/huquqiyaxborot/8882>

The national procedure for systematically solving the problems of women and girls by maintaining the "Women's Notebook" and their social support was approved.

According to it, the following categories of women over 30 years of age are included in the local "Women's Register" in each sector:

- unemployed women and girls in need of social protection;
- needy women who have lost their breadwinners;
- women with group I and II disabilities in need of social assistance;
- women with group I disabilities who need to repair their homes;
- women living in non-residential areas, who do not have a residence in their name or in the name of their family members;
- single women who have one or more dependent children with group I and II disabilities;
- women in need of medical protection (persons who are themselves and their family members living together are in a difficult social situation, have a chronic or severe disabling disease, do not have a disability group, do not have a sufficient source of income);
- women in need of legal assistance;
- women in need of psychological counseling (women suffering from oppression and violence, with social problems).

"Women's notebook" is maintained in the following order:

The problems, needs and interests of women and girls are studied from house to house in the first 15 days of the first month of every half year. Women's problems are identified through a questionnaire, and the identified problems are included in the women's personal individual questionnaires within 3 days. Accordingly, individual questionnaires will be reviewed within 1 day. After that, within 3 days, the questionnaire data will be compared with the data of offices and organizations, and the level (category) of women's need for social protection will be determined.

When analyzing the work in this regard on the example of Samarkand region, which has a high socio-economic indicator, the following will be known. In particular, Resolution 250 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2021 "On additional measures for financial assistance and social support of families, women and youth in need of assistance" In order to ensure the implementation of the decision no., 1927 women were included in the "Women's register" in Samarkand, and practical assistance was provided to all of them.

As of December 2021, 81,000 women were provided targeted assistance within the framework of the system of working with the "Women's Register" of the Samarkand region, and 196.7 billion soums were allocated for this. According to the Ministry of Neighborhoods, 25,144 women in need of social protection were registered in the region, which is 30% of the national level.⁶

At this point, it should be noted that women in need of social protection are divided into the following 6 categories in the region.

- 1) women from low-income families, their number in the region is 10,212 (40.6% of the total number of people in need of social protection);
- 2) 3,926 (15.6%) girls in need of social protection raised in single-parent families;

⁶ [www.http://sam.stat.uz](http://sam.stat.uz)

- 3) 4,967 (19.7%) women in need of social protection whose spouses died and who are raising their minor children alone;
- 4) 2,139 (8.5%) women in needy families with children with disabilities;
- 5) 3,189 (12.8%) women in needy families with one or both parents having disabilities of the 1st or 2nd group;
- 6) There are 711 (2.8%) single women in need of social protection living separately (on rent) raising 2 or more children.

It was determined that the most common reasons for the increase in the number of women in need of social protection are: the need for medical assistance; unemployment; disability of himself and his children; need for housing; the need to allocate land for repeated crops and the need to get a loan to start a business. There are relatively many women in need of social protection in the region: Urgut (9615), Kattakurgan city (2529), Pastdargom (2418), Samarkand city (1658), Samarkand (1405), Ishtikhon (1312), Tayloq (1240) was recorded in such districts. In 2021, the working group of the region and the ministry held dialogues with 150 women in need of social protection in all district (city) neighborhoods and studied their problems.⁷ As a result, the reasons for the increase in the number of women in need of social protection were deeply analyzed and the factors leading to them were identified.

Seminars aimed at improving the quality of the activities of the sectors and the effectiveness of the work being carried out on the socio-economic development of the region are being organized with the participation of sector leaders and secretaries of 16 districts and cities of Samarkand region, as well as the responsible leaders of their respective departments.

It was planned to train 13,700 unemployed women for professions by the General Directorate of Employment together with official organizations, and in practice 15,608 unemployed women were trained for professions. In 2021, 7,357 unemployed women were trained in short vocational training courses at women's entrepreneurship centers, and in 2022, 8,351 unemployed women were trained. Of these, the number of women who received a loan and started their own business is 2779.

In 2019, 2891 in 2020, 7357 in 2021, total of 10644 women were trained by Samarkand region "Women's Entrepreneurship Center", including women in "Women's Register" and 1,704 women have received loans and are conducting their own activities under the "Every family is an entrepreneur" program.

In order to strengthen the activity of the center, new programs will be introduced in 2021, according to which action plans will be developed in the districts and cities of Samarkand region in order to guide and provide employment to women who are listed in the "Women's register" and who need help. released As part of the plan of targeted measures, they participated in seminars organized by international organizations in order to improve the skills of trainers of the entrepreneurship center and received international certificates.

The number of women registered as entrepreneurs was 8,404 in 2021, and 13,737 in 2022. In 2021, the total number of loans allocated to women will be 14,335, and in 2022, they will be 21,105.

In the region, 65,920 women in need of social assistance were included in the "Women's register" and provided with assistance. Employment of 28,570 women and girls was provided.

⁷ [www.http://sam.stat.uz](http://sam.stat.uz)

Loans were allocated to 2,680 women who wanted to get a loan. The amount spent is 32.8 billion soums. Financial assistance was provided to 15,760 needy women without breadwinners. The amount spent is 18.1 billion soums. Material assistance was provided to 11,618 persons with disabilities of groups 1 and 2 in need of social assistance. The amount spent is 12.3 billion soums. Women in need of housing Housing problems of 657 women were solved. Practical assistance was provided to 6570 needy women with disabled children under the care of 23.5 billion soums. The amount spent is 7.1 billion soums. 93.9 bln. soums (61.2 billion soums from the Women's Notebook fund and 32.7 billion soums from a bank loan).⁸

On the state program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the implementation of the action strategy on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of development of science, enlightenment and digital economy"" 2020 In accordance with Decree No. PF-5953 dated March 2, 2015, a decision was made by the Cabinet of Ministers in order to create more opportunities for women to study in higher education institutions.⁹

In addition, in our country, the preferential admission procedure for children of low-income families or women with disabilities to higher education institutions has been introduced, along with the expansion of the ranks of educated women, hundreds of women who are stuck in the vortex of problems in their lives have lost their way from life and society. opportunity is being created for him to find his place.

In the Samarkand region, 51,720 women who are on the permanent list in the 2021-2022 academic year submitted documents to the higher education institutions of the republic. 8,658 of them were recommended to study in higher education institutions. 228 additional state grants were allocated to women from needy families who have lost their breadwinners and are included in the permanent list of "Women's Register" and "Iron Register" in the province.

In short, strengthening the role and position of women in state and community management in the republic is considered one of the most important directions of our reforms. As a result of the work carried out in this regard, indicators of women's gender equality, their education and employment, finding their place and influence in the spheres of public administration are increasing day by day.

Today, about 1,400 women are working in leadership positions in the system of state and public organizations of our Republic. Their share is 82% in the field of healthcare and social services, 72% in the field of science, education, culture and art, 45% in agriculture, and 38% in industry.

In order to strengthen the family, it has become a tradition to hold competitions on "The most exemplary family", "The best mother-in-law", "Educated family", "Book-loving family". These activities help to increase exemplary families in the process of publicizing their achievements, as examples of united families and mutually loving in-laws.

⁸ 2022 data of the Department of Family and Women of Samarkand region.

⁹ <http://www.lex.uz>

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